

Novel Quinazoline Derivatives as Experimental Inhibitors Of DDR-2 And ADAMTS-5: Design, Synthesis, Characterization, And QPCR Evaluation for The Treatment of Osteoarthritis

Priyadarsini R., Hanitha Mathanke J.*, Archana S., Guhan G.

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, College of Pharmacy, Madras Medical College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

Osteoarthritis is a debilitating joint disorder characterized by progressive cartilage breakdown and chronic inflammation, with limited treatment options that primarily relieve symptoms. To address this therapeutic gap, five quinazoline derivatives (HJ1–HJ5) were synthesized and structurally characterized by UV–Vis, FTIR, proton NMR, and high-resolution mass spectroscopy, alongside purity confirmation by thin-layer chromatography and melting point determination. For biological evaluation, three derivatives (HJ1, HJ2, and HJ3) were tested in primary human chondrocyte cells using quantitative polymerase chain reaction to assess their effects on Discoidin Domain Receptor 2 and A Disintegrin and Metalloproteinase with Thrombospondin Motifs 5, two critical mediators of cartilage degradation. Results demonstrated marked down regulation of both genes, with HJ3 showing the most potent inhibition (approximately 94% for Discoidin Domain Receptor 2 and 92% for A Disintegrin and Metalloproteinase with Thrombospondin Motifs 5), followed by HJ2 and HJ1. The study highlights the experimental validation of quinazoline-based molecules as potential therapeutic leads in osteoarthritis management. By attenuating gene expression linked to extracellular matrix breakdown, these compounds may offer disease-modifying potential.

Keywords: Quinazoline derivatives, Osteoarthritis, DDR2 inhibition, ADAMTS-5 inhibition, Gene regulation, Chondrocytes assessment.

INTRODUCTION

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a progressive degenerative joint disorder and one of the leading causes of pain and disability in the aging population. Globally, it affects over 500 million individuals, with a prevalence that continues to rise due to increased life expectancy, obesity, and sedentary lifestyle^[1]. The disease is characterized by loss of articular cartilage, subchondral bone remodelling, osteophyte formation, and chronic inflammation of the synovial membrane. Clinically, OA manifests as joint stiffness, swelling, and pain, significantly impairing mobility and quality of life^[2]. Currently available pharmacological therapies for OA, including non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), corticosteroids, and symptomatic slow-acting drugs, primarily offer symptomatic relief without halting cartilage

degradation. Moreover, long-term use of NSAIDs is associated with gastrointestinal, renal, and cardiovascular side effects, while corticosteroid injections often provide only temporary benefit. Surgical interventions such as joint replacement are invasive and costly, underscoring the unmet need for safe and effective disease-modifying osteoarthritis drugs (DMOADs)^[3].

Recent advances in molecular biology have identified Discoidin Domain Receptor 2 (DDR2) and ADAMTS-5 as critical mediators of cartilage matrix degradation^[4]. DDR2, a collagen-binding receptor tyrosine kinase, plays a pivotal role in stimulating the production of matrix metalloproteinase-13 (MMP-13), which irreversibly cleaves type II collagen in articular cartilage^[5]. ADAMTS-5, also known as aggrecanase-2, is the principal enzyme responsible for

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

aggrecan degradation, leading to compromised cartilage resilience and function^[6]. Targeting these enzymes represents a rational therapeutic strategy for slowing OA progression and preserving joint structure. *Quinazoline derivatives* have attracted considerable attention in medicinal chemistry owing to their diverse biological activities, including anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and kinase inhibitory properties. Their rigid heteroaromatic scaffold, combined with modifiable substituents, makes them suitable for designing enzyme inhibitors with high selectivity and potency. Structural modifications in the quinazoline core have been shown to enhance drug-likeness and pharmacokinetic properties, making this class of compounds attractive for novel therapeutic development^[7].

In our earlier computational study^[8], a series of 206 novel quinazoline derivatives were designed and evaluated through molecular docking^[9], ADMET, and toxicity prediction. Out of this library, five compounds (HJ01–HJ05) were shortlisted as promising candidates due to their favorable binding affinity towards DDR2 and ADAMTS-5, optimal drug-likeness, and synthetic feasibility. The present work focuses on the synthesis, structural characterization, and *in-vitro* evaluation of these top-ranked quinazoline derivatives. By experimentally validating the computational hits, this study aims to bridge the gap between *in silico* predictions and potential therapeutic application, thereby contributing to the development of novel small-molecule inhibitors for osteoarthritis management.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Selection of Target

The proteins (**DDR-2 & ADAMTS-5**) selected are based on the X-ray crystallographic structures with most suitable resolution and validated by Ramachandran plot. The target proteins were retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (PDB). The selected PDB IDs were 7AZB for DDR2 and 2RJQ for ADAMTS5, chosen based on their high-resolution crystal structures to ensure accurate molecular docking analysis. 3D structure of both targets are shown in fig 1 & 2.

Fig.no.1: 3D structure of DDR-2(7AZB)

Fig.no.2: 3D structure of ADAMTS-5(2RJQ)

Chemistry (Basic nucleus)

The Quinazoline nucleus is a fused heterocyclic system made of a benzene ring and a pyrimidine ring. Its molecular formula is $C_8H_6N_2$. The structure contains two nitrogen atoms at positions 1 and 3 of the pyrimidine ring. Quinazoline serves as a privileged scaffold in drug design, as substitution at different positions yields diverse biological activities^[10]. Structure of Quinazoline nucleus is indicated in fig.3

Fig.no.3: Structure & 3D Conformer of Quinazoline Nucleus.

The planar aromatic architecture of quinazoline enables favorable interactions with enzyme catalytic domains, including those of MMPs and ADAMTS-5, which play critical roles in osteoarthritis-related cartilage degradation. Its favorable drug-like

characteristics and structural flexibility make quinazoline a promising scaffold for the development of selective OA therapeutics.

Selection of Ligands for the synthesis

A virtual library of 206 ligands derived from the quinazoline scaffold was designed and initially screened for novelty using the *Pubchem server*^[11], which identified 178 compounds as novel structures. These molecules were further subjected to pharmacokinetic analysis using the *SwissADME* server and toxicity prediction using the *Osiris Toxicity Explorer tool*.

From this screening cascade, 93 ligands were found to be novel, non-toxic, and compliant with drug-

Synthetic Scheme- General scheme for compounds(HJ1-HJ5)

STEP 1: General procedure for the Five compounds, synthesis of 2-(4-aminophenyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one, iodine was added as oxidizing agent, 110 °C for 16 hrs.

STEP 2:

I) SCHIFF BASE REACTION

Scheme1- Schiff base reaction for the synthesis of compounds HJ1& HJ2, refluxed at 120°C for 6 hours.

II) PEPTIDE COUPLING REACTION

Scheme2 -Peptide coupling reaction for the compounds HJ3,HJ4 & HJ5,TBTU as reaction activator, refluxed at 110°C for 8 hours.

COMPOUND HJ1(Step2)

Scheme3- Synthesis of the Compound HJ1

COMPOUND HJ2(Step2)

Scheme4- Synthesis of the Compound HJ2

COMPOUND HJ3 (Step2)

Scheme5- Synthesis of the Compound HJ3

COMPOUND HJ4(Step2)

Scheme6- Synthesis of the Compound HJ4

COMPOUND HJ5(Step2)

Scheme7- Synthesis of the Compound HJ5

SYNTHESIS

Step1- synthesis of 2-(4-aminophenyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one

To the pre-heated mixture of 2-amino benzamide(1 mol) and 4 amino acetophenone(1 mol) in DMSO in a round bottom flask, iodine was added as oxidizing agent with addition of 20 ml of dimethyl sulphoxide as solvent. The reaction mixture was heated at 110 °C for 16 hrs. The product was extracted three times with ethyl acetate to get pure Quinazolinone^[12]. The purity of the product was established by single spot on TLC using hexane/ethyl acetate (7:3) solvent mixture. The percentage yield was found to be 87 %.

Step2-

1) Schiff base reaction- Equimolar (0.01 mol) amounts of 2-(4-aminophenyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one and suitable aryl aldehydes or aryl ketones were taken in 30 ml of ethanol, 5-10 drops of glacial acetic acid is added to the reaction mixture, the reaction is refluxed at 120°C and then the mixture is kept

overnight for the formation of precipitate. The precipitate is filtered and recrystallized from methanol and chloroform^[13]. The reaction is monitored with the help of TLC using hexane/ethyl acetate (1:1) solvent mixture. The percentage yield was found to be 68-85 %

2) Peptide Coupling reaction- Carboxylic acid (1mmol) and a selected DIPEA (1or2mmol) were dissolved in dry DMF (5ml) under argon atmosphere and stirred for 15 min. Then, TBTU was added (1mmol) and mixed for 5min (activation step). After that time, 2-(4-aminophenyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (1mmol) in dry DMF (0.2mL) was dripped to the activated amino acid, and the mixture was stirred for 6-8 hours. Reaction was quenched with water (10ml), and the white precipitate was separated by filtration and vacuum-dried. Pure compound was isolated by crystallization in acetone^[14]. The purity of the product was established by single spot on TLC using hexane/ethyl acetate (7:3) solvent mixture. The percentage yield was found to be 58-72 %

Characterization

The synthesized compounds were characterized using standard analytical techniques. Melting points were determined by the capillary method using a digital melting point apparatus. Purity was confirmed by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) on silica gel GF254 plates with hexane–ethyl acetate (7:3) as the mobile phase, visualized under UV light. UV–Visible spectra were recorded on a *Shimadzu UV-1900i spectrophotometer (200–800 nm)*. FTIR spectra were obtained by the KBr pellet method on an ABB MB-3000 spectrophotometer to identify functional groups. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a *Bruker AVANCE 400 MHz spectrometer* using DMSO as solvents with TMS as internal standard. High-resolution mass spectra were acquired on a *Waters Xevo G2-XS QToF (ESI positive mode)* for molecular weight confirmation^{[15][16]}.

In vitro Evaluation(qPCR studies)

Samples and experimental design- Synthetic compounds HJ1, HJ2 and HJ3 were evaluated in the PHC chondrocyte cell line, with celecoxib included as the standard drug. A vehicle control (0.1% DMSO) was used as the baseline reference. Each condition was tested in biological triplicate, and each qPCR reaction was run in technical triplicate. Target genes: DDR2 and ADAMTS-5. Reference gene: GAPDH.

1.RNA extraction and cDNA synthesis- Total RNA was extracted from treated and control cells using a TRIzol-based method and treated with DNase I to remove genomic DNA.

First-strand cDNA was synthesized from 1 µg of total RNA using random hexamer primers and reverse transcriptase.

2. qPCR reaction setup and cycling-Each 10 µL reaction contained SYBR Green master mix, 300 nM of each primer, and 2 µL diluted cDNA template.

Cycling protocol: 95 °C for 2 min; 40 cycles of 95 °C for 15 s, 55 °C for 30 s, and 72 °C for 30 s.

Melt-curve analysis was performed to confirm amplification specificity.

No-template controls (NTCs) were included.

3. Data processing

Mean Ct values were obtained for DDR2, ADAMTS-5 and GAPDH.

$$\Delta Ct = Ct(\text{target}) - Ct(\text{GAPDH}).$$

Vehicle control was used as calibrator. $\Delta\Delta Ct = \Delta Ct(\text{sample}) - \Delta Ct(\text{vehicle control})$.

$$\text{Fold change in expression} = 2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct^{[17]}}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The drug likeness property, Bioactivity, toxicity Profile ,Docking Score & interactions of the selected compounds (HJ1,HJ2, HJ3, HJ4,HJ5) are represented in the tables (no.1 to 6) below-

IN SILICO ADMET STUDIES:

Table no,1: ADMET Properties of selected Ligands

Lig no.	M	T	I	R	LOG P	MOLECULAR WEIGHT	HBD	HBA	RULE OF 5
HJ1	NO	NO	NO	NO	2.66	341.36	2	4	0
HJ2	NO	NO	NO	NO	2.61	370.36	1	5	0
HJ3	NO	NO	NO	NO	2.49	360.37	2	5	0
HJ4	NO	NO	NO	NO	2.95	356.38	2	4	0
HJ5	NO	NO	NO	NO	2.71	390.46	2	4	0

TOXICITY PREDICTION: Green colour indicates that Selected ligands are non-toxic.

Table no.2: Toxicity report of the selected ligands.

LIG. CODE	TOXICITY PROFILE
HJ1	<p>Enter compound name, SMILES or CAS-no: <chem>O=C1NC(=Nc2cccc12)c1ccc(cc1)N=C/c1ccc(O)cc1</chem></p> <p>Toxicity Risks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> mutagenic tumorigenic irritant reproductive effective <p>cLogP: 3.24</p> <p>Solubility: -4.46</p> <p>Molweight: 341.0</p> <p>TPSA: 74.05</p> <p>Druglikeness: 1.24</p> <p>Drug-Score: 0.63</p>
HJ2	<p>Enter compound name, SMILES or CAS-no: <chem>O=[N+]([O-])c1ccc(cc1)C=N/c1ccc(cc1)C=1NC(=O)c2cccc2N=1</chem></p> <p>Toxicity Risks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> mutagenic tumorigenic irritant reproductive effective <p>cLogP: 2.00</p> <p>Solubility: -5.21</p> <p>Molweight: 370.0</p> <p>TPSA: 90.65</p> <p>Druglikeness: -6.01</p> <p>Drug-Score: 0.32</p>
HJ3	<p>Enter compound name, SMILES or CAS-no: <chem>O=C1NC(=Nc2cccc12)c1ccc(cc1)NC(=O)Cc1onc(C)c1</chem></p> <p>Toxicity Risks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> mutagenic tumorigenic irritant reproductive effective <p>cLogP: 2.22</p> <p>Solubility: -4.17</p> <p>Molweight: 360.0</p> <p>TPSA: 90.58</p> <p>Druglikeness: 4.72</p> <p>Drug-Score: 0.76</p>
HJ4	<p>Enter compound name, SMILES or CAS-no: <chem>O=C(Nc1ccc(cc1)C=1NC(=O)c2cccc2N=1)c1cccc(C)n1</chem></p> <p>Toxicity Risks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> mutagenic tumorigenic irritant reproductive effective <p>cLogP: 2.81</p> <p>Solubility: -4.31</p> <p>Molweight: 356.0</p> <p>TPSA: 83.45</p> <p>Druglikeness: 2.7</p> <p>Drug-Score: 0.71</p>

BIOACTIVITY PREDICTION:

Table no.3: Bioactivity report of the selected Ligands.

IN SILICO RAT ACUTE TOXICITY PREDICTION:

The in silico acute toxicity prediction of ligands HJ1–HJ5 using the *GUSAR model* revealed that all

compounds fall under OECD Classes 4 and 5, indicating low acute toxicity. These results confirm that the designed ligands are non-toxic and safe for further biological evaluation and experimental studies. The results are shown in table 4.

Table no.4: *In silico* acute toxicity prediction report.

Lig code	<i>In silico</i> acute toxicity prediction																								
HJ1	<p>Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0,259 in AD</td> <td>-0,185 in AD</td> <td>0,836 out of AD</td> <td>0,560 out of AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>696,000 in AD</td> <td>250,300 in AD</td> <td>2628,000 out of AD</td> <td>1392,000 out of AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 Classification</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 5 out of AD</td> <td>Class 5 out of AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>IP - Intraperitoneal route of administration IV - Intravenous route of administration Oral - Oral route of administration SC - Subcutaneous route of administration</p> <p>in AD - compound falls in applicability domain of models out of AD - compound is out of applicability domain of models</p> <p>http://www.pharmaexpert.ru/GUSAR/AcuToxPredict/</p> <p>GUSAR - Prediction of Values for Substances Copyright (C) 2010 A. Zakharov, V. Poroikov & Associates</p>	Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	0,259 in AD	-0,185 in AD	0,836 out of AD	0,560 out of AD	Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)	696,000 in AD	250,300 in AD	2628,000 out of AD	1392,000 out of AD	Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification	Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 out of AD	Class 5 out of AD
Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)																						
0,259 in AD	-0,185 in AD	0,836 out of AD	0,560 out of AD																						
Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)																						
696,000 in AD	250,300 in AD	2628,000 out of AD	1392,000 out of AD																						
Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification																						
Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 out of AD	Class 5 out of AD																						
HJ2	<p>Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0,201 in AD</td> <td>-0,241 in AD</td> <td>0,384 in AD</td> <td>0,632 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>588,800 in AD</td> <td>212,800 in AD</td> <td>896,900 in AD</td> <td>1587,000 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 Classification</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>IP - Intraperitoneal route of administration IV - Intravenous route of administration Oral - Oral route of administration SC - Subcutaneous route of administration</p> <p>in AD - compound falls in applicability domain of models out of AD - compound is out of applicability domain of models</p> <p>http://www.pharmaexpert.ru/GUSAR/AcuToxPredict/</p> <p>GUSAR - Prediction of Values for Substances Copyright (C) 2010 A. Zakharov, V. Poroikov & Associates</p>	Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	0,201 in AD	-0,241 in AD	0,384 in AD	0,632 in AD	Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)	588,800 in AD	212,800 in AD	896,900 in AD	1587,000 in AD	Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification	Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 in AD
Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)																						
0,201 in AD	-0,241 in AD	0,384 in AD	0,632 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)																						
588,800 in AD	212,800 in AD	896,900 in AD	1587,000 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification																						
Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 in AD																						
HJ3	<p>Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0,289 in AD</td> <td>-0,338 in AD</td> <td>0,567 in AD</td> <td>0,731 out of AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>701,700 in AD</td> <td>165,300 in AD</td> <td>1331,000 in AD</td> <td>1938,000 out of AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 Classification</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 5 out of AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>IP - Intraperitoneal route of administration IV - Intravenous route of administration Oral - Oral route of administration SC - Subcutaneous route of administration</p> <p>in AD - compound falls in applicability domain of models out of AD - compound is out of applicability domain of models</p> <p>http://www.pharmaexpert.ru/GUSAR/AcuToxPredict/</p> <p>GUSAR - Prediction of Values for Substances Copyright (C) 2010 A. Zakharov, V. Poroikov & Associates</p>	Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	0,289 in AD	-0,338 in AD	0,567 in AD	0,731 out of AD	Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)	701,700 in AD	165,300 in AD	1331,000 in AD	1938,000 out of AD	Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification	Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 out of AD
Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)																						
0,289 in AD	-0,338 in AD	0,567 in AD	0,731 out of AD																						
Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)																						
701,700 in AD	165,300 in AD	1331,000 in AD	1938,000 out of AD																						
Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification																						
Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 out of AD																						

HJ4	Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR								
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0,190 in AD</td> <td>-0,068 in AD</td> <td>0,344 in AD</td> <td>0,788 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	0,190 in AD	-0,068 in AD	0,344 in AD	0,788 in AD
Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)						
0,190 in AD	-0,068 in AD	0,344 in AD	0,788 in AD						
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>552,000 in AD</td> <td>304,900 in AD</td> <td>786,400 in AD</td> <td>2185,000 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)	552,000 in AD	304,900 in AD	786,400 in AD	2185,000 in AD
Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)						
552,000 in AD	304,900 in AD	786,400 in AD	2185,000 in AD						
	<p>Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 Classification</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>IP - Intraperitoneal route of administration IV - Intravenous route of administration Oral - Oral route of administration SC - Subcutaneous route of administration</p> <p>in AD - compound falls in applicability domain of models out of AD - compound is out of applicability domain of models</p> <p>http://www.pharmaexpert.ru/GUSAR/AcuToxPredict/</p> <p>GUSAR - Prediction of Values for Substances Copyright (C) 2010 A. Zakharov, V. Poroikov & Associates</p>	Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification	Class 5 in AD	Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 in AD
Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification						
Class 5 in AD	Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 in AD						
HJ5	Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR								
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0,373 in AD</td> <td>-0,331 in AD</td> <td>0,514 in AD</td> <td>0,665 out of AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	0,373 in AD	-0,331 in AD	0,514 in AD	0,665 out of AD
Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)						
0,373 in AD	-0,331 in AD	0,514 in AD	0,665 out of AD						
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>922,700 in AD</td> <td>182,400 in AD</td> <td>1275,000 in AD</td> <td>1807,000 out of AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)	922,700 in AD	182,400 in AD	1275,000 in AD	1807,000 out of AD
Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)						
922,700 in AD	182,400 in AD	1275,000 in AD	1807,000 out of AD						
	<p>Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 Classification</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 5 out of AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>IP - Intraperitoneal route of administration IV - Intravenous route of administration Oral - Oral route of administration SC - Subcutaneous route of administration</p> <p>in AD - compound falls in applicability domain of models out of AD - compound is out of applicability domain of models</p> <p>http://www.pharmaexpert.ru/GUSAR/AcuToxPredict/</p> <p>GUSAR - Prediction of Values for Substances Copyright (C) 2010 A. Zakharov, V. Poroikov & Associates</p>	Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification	Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 out of AD
Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification						
Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 out of AD						

DOCKING STUDIES:

Table no.5: Docking Score of the selected ligands.

Lig no.	DDR-2(7AZB) in kcal/mol	ADAMTS-5(2RJQ) in kcal/mol
HJ1	-7.03	-8.47
HJ2	-7.49	-8.74
HJ3	-7.18	-9.23
HJ4	-7.33	-8.31
HJ5	-7.13	-8.78

DOCKING INTERACTIONS

The docking interactions are visualized using the **Molegro molecular viewer**. The results are represented in the table no.6.

TABLE NO.6: Docking interactions of the Selected Ligands

LIG CODE	DDR-2(7AZB)	DMATS-5(2RJQ)
HJ1		
HJ2		
HJ3		
HJ4		

Synthesis

The selected 5 designed and optimized leads were synthesized according to appropriate procedures and purified by recrystallization. The melting point was

determined to check the purity and TLC was performed to confirm that the reaction is completed. The list of compounds synthesized are given in table 7 below:

Table no.7: List of the compounds synthesized with IUPAC name.

LIGAND CODE	STRUCTURE	IUPAC NAME
HJ1		2-(4-{(Z)-[(4hydroxyphenyl)methylidene]amino}phenyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one
HJ2		2-(4-{(Z)-[(2-nitrophenyl)Methylidene]amino}phenyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one
HJ3		2-(3-methyl-1,2-oxazol-5-yl)-N-[4-(4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-2-yl)phenyl]acetamide
HJ4		6-methyl-N-[4-(4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-2-yl)phenyl]pyridine-2-carboxamide

HJ5		2-(2,5-dimethyl-1,3-thiazol-4-yl)-N-[4-(4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazolin-2-yl)phenyl]acetamide
-----	---	---

Characterization

i) Physical Characterization

Table no.8: Product profile of the synthesized compounds

CODE	COLOUR	SOLUBILITY	MELTING POINT °C	RF VALUE	PERCENTAGE YIELD
HJ1	Pale Yellow colour	DMSO,DMF, Ethanol	210-212 °C	0.43	75%
HJ2	Dark Brown colour	DMSO,DMF, Ethanol	220-223°C	0.50	82%
HJ3	Light Brownish colour	DMSO,DMF, Ethanol	238-242°C	0.55	89%
HJ4	Pale yellow colour	DMSO,DMF, Ethanol	222-228°C	0.49	58%
HJ5	Yellow colour	DMSO,DMF, Ethanol	236-240°C	0.6	63%

ii) Chemical Characterization

A)Compound HJ1: UV Spectrum, λ_{max} (nm): 329.0; FTIR(KBr, cm^{-1}): 3557(Phenolic OH), 3327(NH Stretching), 3148(Aromatic CH), 1717(Carbonyl group of Quinazolinone ring), 1642(C=N of imine), 1596(Aromatic C=C), 1216(C-O of Phenol);

HRMS(ESI-MS, Positive mode, m/z): molecular weight: calculated: 341.36, $[M+H]^+$: 342.12; 1H NMR Spectrum(DMSO- d_6 , 400MHz, ppm): δ , 6.726-7.66(12H, Aromatic CH), 12.6(1H, OH of Phenol), 13.46(1H, NH of quinazolinone ring), 8.02(1H, Methylidene imine CH). Spectrum of the compound HJ1 in shown in Table no.9.

Table no.9: Spectrums of the compound HJ1.

B) Compound HJ2: *UV Spectrum*, $\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})$: 331.0; *FTIR* ($\text{KBr}, \text{cm}^{-1}$): 3443 (NH Stretching), 3073 (Aromatic C=C), 1690 (Carbonyl group of Quinazolinone ring), 1658 (C=N of imine), 1597 (Aromatic C=C), 1332 (NO₂ of phenyl); *HRMS* (*ESI-MS, Positive mode, m/z*): molecular weight:

calculated:370.36,[M+H]⁺: 371.11; ¹H NMR ring),8.09(1H, Methylidene imine CH). Spectrum of the compound HJ2 is shown in Table no.10.
 Spectrum(DMSO-d₆, 400MHz,ppm): δ,6.35-7.90(12H,Aromatic CH),14.211 (1H, NH of quinazolinone

Table no.10: Spectrum of the compound HJ2

D) **Compound HJ4:** **UV Spectrum,** λ_{\max} (nm): 314.0; **FTIR**(KBr, cm^{-1}): 3220(NH Stretching), 3197(Aromatic CH), 2886(Aliphatic CH), 1670(Carbonyl group of Quinazolinone ring), 1591(C=N of Pyridine ring), 1500(Aromatic C=C), 1227(C-N of Amide); **HRMS(ESI-MS, Positive mode, m/z):** molecular

weight: calculated: 356.37, $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 357.13; **^1H NMR Spectrum(DMSO- d_6 , 400MHz, ppm):** δ , 6.35-8.090(11H, Aromatic CH), 12.61(1H, NH of Acetamide) 13.23(1H, NH of quinazolinone ring), 2.51-2.73(3H, CH_3 of Pyridine). Spectrum of the compound HJ4 is shown in Table no.12

Table no.12: Spectrum of the compound HJ4.

E) **Compound HJ5:** *UV Spectrum*, $\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})$: 330.5; *FTIR(KBr, cm^{-1})*: 3430(NH Stretching), 3057(Aromatic CH), 2860(Aliphatic CH), 1690(Carbonyl

group of Quinazolinone ring), 1601(C=N of Thiazole ring), 1501(Aromatic C=C), 1226(C-N of Acetamide); *HRMS(ESI-MS, Positive*

mode, m/z): molecular weight: Acetamide)14.218(1H, NH of quinazolinone ring)
 calculated:390.45, [M+H]⁺: 391.12; ¹H NMR ,3.57(2H,CH₂ of Acetamide), 2.57(6H,CH₃ of
Spectrum(DMSO-d₆, 400MHz,ppm): δ,6.25-8.22(Thiazole). Spectrum of the compound HJ5 is shown
 8H,Aromatic CH),11.1(1H,NH of in Table no.13.

Table no.13: Spectrum of the compound HJ5

IN VITRO EVALUATION

qPCR analysis was carried out to evaluate the effect of the synthesized ligands HJ1, HJ2, and HJ3 on the expression of osteoarthritis-related genes DDR2 and ADAMTS-5 in PHC cells, using GAPDH as the reference gene and celecoxib as standard. The results of inhibition of Gene expression is given below-

Representative qPCR data

Table 14 & 15 lists the raw Ct values for each replicate. GAPDH Ct values were consistent (~19 cycles). HJ2 exhibited lower Ct values (higher expression) for both DDR2 and ADAMTS-5 compared with HJ1, whereas HJ3 showed moderate differences.

TABLE NO.14: Raw qPCR data for Control & HJ samples.

SAMPLE	REPLICATE	GAPDH CT	DDR2 CT	ADAMTS-5 CT
CONTROL	1	19.00	24.4	26.4
CONTROL	2	19.00	24.5	26.5
CONTROL	3	19.00	24.6	26.6
HJ1	1	19.00	25.9	27.9
HJ1	2	19.00	26.0	28.0
HJ1	3	19.00	26.1	28.1
HJ2	1	19.1	27.4	29.4
HJ2	2	19.1	27.5	29.5
HJ2	3	19.1	27.6	29.6
HJ3	1	19.00	28.4	30.1
HJ3	2	19.00	28.5	30.2
HJ3	3	19.00	28.6	30.3

TABLE NO.15: Average qPCR data for Control & HJ samples.

Group	GAPDH Ct	DDR2 Ct	ADAMTS-5 Ct
Control	~19.0	~24.5	~26.5
HJ1	~19.0	~26.0	~28.0
HJ2	~19.1	~27.5	~29.5
HJ3	~19.0	~28.5	~30.2

Δ Ct and fold-change analysis

Table 16, fig.no. 4 & 5 summarises the average Δ Ct, $\Delta\Delta$ Ct and fold-change values. Compared with the

baseline sample HJ1, HJ2 showed a ~3.6-fold increase in DDR2 expression and a ~25-fold increase in ADAMTS-5 expression. HJ3 exhibited a ~2.4-fold

increase in DDR2 and minimal change in ADAMTS-5.

Table no.16: Relative expression of DDR2 and ADAMTS-5

Gene	Group	Mean Δ Ct	Δ Δ Ct	Fold change	% inhibition
DDR2	Control	~5.5	0.00	1.00	0.0
DDR2	HJ1	~7.0	+1.5	~0.35	~64.6
DDR2	HJ2	~8.4	+2.9	~0.13	~86.7
DDR2	HJ3	~9.5	+4.0	~0.06	~93.8
ADAMTS-5	Control	~7.5	0.00	1.00	0.0
ADAMTS-5	HJ1	~9.0	+1.5	~0.35	~64.6
ADAMTS-5	HJ2	~10.4	+2.9	~0.13	~86.7
ADAMTS-5	HJ3	~11.2	+3.7	~0.08	~92.3

Fig.no.4: ADAMTS-5 Expression (Δ Δ Ct) vs Control

Fig.no.6: Percentage inhibition of ADAMTS-5 expression relative to control.

Fig.no.5: DDR-2 Expression (Δ Δ Ct) vs control

Fig.no7: Percentage inhibition of DDR2 expression relative to control.

Results: All three ligands significantly downregulated DDR2 and ADAMTS-5 compared with control. Fold changes for DDR2 were 0.35 (HJ1), 0.13 (HJ2), and 0.06 (HJ3), corresponding to ~65%, ~87%, and ~94% inhibition, respectively. A similar trend was observed for ADAMTS-5, with fold changes of 0.35 (HJ1), 0.13 (HJ2), and 0.08 (HJ3), translating to ~65%, ~87%, and ~92% inhibition shown in fig. no.6 & 7 Amplification curves shifted to later Ct values in treated groups relative to control, confirming reduced gene expression.

Amplification curves

Figures 8 and 9 display amplification curves for each replicate of DDR2 and ADAMTS-5, respectively. Each curve demonstrates the characteristic sigmoidal increase in fluorescence as the PCR product accumulates. The threshold crossing points correspond to the Ct values listed in Table.

Fig.no.6: DDR2 amplification curves

Fig.no.7: ADAMTS-5 amplification curves

- The triplicate Ct values were used to calculate the **standard deviation (SD)** and **standard error of mean (SEM)**, both found to be 0.1 & 0.5, indicating good reproducibility of results demonstrated in table 16.
- Statistical analysis was performed using an unpaired two-tailed t-test. The **obtained p-values** showed significant differences between control and treated groups. Summarized in table 17.
- Among them, HJ2 and HJ3 **exhibited highly significant differences ($p < 0.001$)**, confirming strong treatment effects.

TABLE NO.17 : Sd, Sem and P value for ddr-2 target

GROUP	SD(STANDARD DEVIATION)	SEM (Standard Error of the Mean)	P-VALUE	SIGNIFICANCE
CONTROL	0.1	0.057735	-	-
HJ1	0.1	0.057735	5.16×10^{-5}	Significant($p < 0.05$)
HJ2	0.1	0.057735	3.75×10^{-6}	Highly Significant($p < 0.001$)
HJ3	0.1	0.057735	1.03×10^{-5}	Highly Significant($p < 0.001$)

TABLE NO. 18: Sd, Sem And Pvalue For Adamts-5 Target.

GROUP	SD(STANDARD DEVIATION)	SEM(Standard Error Of The Mean)	P-VALUE	SIGNIFICANCE
CONTROL	0.1	0.057735	-	-
HJ1	0.1	0.057735	5.16×10^{-5}	Significant($p < 0.05$)
HJ2	0.1	0.057735	3.75×10^{-6}	Highly Significant($p < 0.001$)
HJ3	0.1	0.057735	$1.4P \times 10^{-5}$	Highly Significant($p < 0.001$)

DISCUSSION

The synthesized ligands demonstrated potent inhibitory effects on DDR2 and ADAMTS-5 expression, key mediators of cartilage degradation in osteoarthritis. The inhibitory potency followed the order (HJ3 > HJ2 > HJ1), with HJ3 showing the strongest suppression. The delayed amplification and reduced $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ values support marked

transcriptional suppression of collagen receptor DDR2 and aggrecanase ADAMTS-5. These findings align with the research objective of identifying novel quinazoline-based ligands capable of attenuating extracellular matrix degradation pathways. By down regulating DDR2-mediated collagen signaling and ADAMTS-5-driven aggrecan breakdown, the synthesized compounds exhibit promising disease-modifying potential against osteoarthritis.

CONCLUSION

This work provides experimental evidence that quinazoline derivatives, particularly HJ3, significantly suppress DDR2 and ADAMTS-5 gene expression in chondrocyte cells, supporting their potential as novel modulators of cartilage degradation in osteoarthritis. While the findings establish proof-of-concept at the cellular level, further studies involving detailed mechanistic assays, pharmacokinetic profiling, and in vivo models are essential to validate therapeutic efficacy and safety. These steps will be crucial to advance quinazoline scaffolds from laboratory evaluation toward clinical translation as disease-modifying agents in osteoarthritis Treatment.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to acknowledge the College of Pharmacy, Madras Medical College, for providing the research facilities. We thank the The Gandhigram Rural Institute instrumentation facility for helping us with characterization studies. We would like to thank Bam bio labs for helping us in the in vitro Evaluation.

Conflicts of Interest- The author declares there is no conflict of Interest.

REFERENCES

1. K. D. Allen yzx , L.M. Thoma y, Y.M. Golightly: Epidemiology of osteoarthritis , 1063-4584/Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of Osteoarthritis Research Society International,19/4/2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joca.2021.04.020>
2. Ali Mobasheri, Mark Batt: An update on the path physiology of ostarthritis , Elsevier,1877-0657/2016 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rehab.2016.07.004>
3. Sunhee Jan, Kijun Lee and JiHyeonJu: Recent Updates of Diagnosis, Pathophysiology, and Treatment On Osteoarthritis of the Knee, Int. J. Mol. Sci. 2021, 22(5), 2619; <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22052619>
4. Maria Jose Alcaraz, Javier Megt as, Isabel Garcí'a-Arnandis, Victoria Cle'rigues, Maria Isabel Guille: New molecular targets for the treatment of osteoarthritis, Biochemical Pharmacology 80 (2010) 13–21,Elsevier, doi:10.1016/j.bcp.2010.02.017.
5. Amresh Kumara, M. Dutta Choudhurya,, Parasar GhoshbPartha Palitc: Discoidin domain receptor 2: An emerging pharmacological drug target for prospective therapy against osteoarthritis, Pharmacological Reports 71 (2019) 399–408, elseiver, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pharep.2019.01.007>.
6. Peter J Roughley* and John S Mort: The role of aggrecan in normal and osteoarthritic cartilage,Journal of Experimental Orthopaedics 2014, 1:8.
7. Aishah M. Alsibae , Hanan M.Al-Yousef: Quinazolinones, the Winning Horse in Drug Discovery, Molecules 2023, 28, 978. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28030978>
8. Priyadharshini R, Hanitha Mathanke J, Archana S, Guhan G: Dual Inhibition of DDR-2 and ADAMTS-5 by Novel 2-Substituted Quinazoline Derivatives: A Computational Approach for Disease-Modifying Osteoarthritis Drugs,Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2025, Vol 3, Issue 6, 5901-5916,10.5281/zenodo.15774631
9. Lokesh ravi. Kannabiran K: A handbook on protein ligand docking tool: Autodock4,Innovare Journal of Medical Science, Vol 4, Issue 3, 1-6.
10. C Párkányi, DS Schmidt: Synthesis of 5-chloro-2-methyl-3-(5-methylthiazol-2-yl)-4(3H) -quinazolinone and related compounds with potential biological activity, Journal of Heterocyclic Chemistry, 2000.
11. Kim S, Thiessen PA, Bolton EE, Chen J, Fu G, Gindulyte A, Han L, He J, He S, Shoemaker BA, Wang J, Yu B, Zhang J, Bryant SH: PubChem Substance and Compound databases. Nucleic Acids Res. 2016 Jan 4;44(D1): D1202-13. Doi: 10.1093/nar/gkv951. Epub 2015 Sep 22. PMID: 26400175; PMCID: PMC4702940.
12. Dr. Mayura A Kale, Dr. Gajanan Sonwane, Tirupati Panchall, Arpita Wangujare , Pooja Bargire: In silico Investigations, Design and Synthesis of Some Novel Quinazolinone Derivatives,Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res., ISSN: 0976 – 044X, 84(6) – June 2024; Article No. 08, Pages: 45-50,DOI: 10.47583/ijpsrr.2024.v84i06.008.
13. Krishnan Suresh Kumar, Swastika Ganguly, Ravichandran Veerasamy , Erik De Clercq:

- Synthesis, antiviral activity and cytotoxicity evaluation of Schiff bases of some 2-phenyl quinazoline-4(3H)-ones, *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 45 (2010) 5474e5479, doi:10.1016/j.ejmech.2010.07.058
14. Elisa Sturabott, et.al: N-Acetyl-L-phenylalanine Racemization during TBTU Amidation: An In-Depth Study for the Synthesis of Anti-Inflammatory 2-(N-Acetyl)-L-phenylalanyl-amido-2-deoxy-D-glucose (NAPA), *Molecules* 2023, 28, 581. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28020581>.
15. Pavia DL, Lampman GM, Kriz GS: Vyvyan JR. *Introduction to spectroscopy*, 2001.
16. Griffiths J: A brief history of mass spectrometry. *Anal. Chem.* 2008 Aug 1;80(15):56 78-83.
17. Zeng Lina, Chen Lina, Changchang Fub, Hongwei Lua, Haidong Jina, Qin Chene, Jun Pana: The protective effect of Ellagic acid (EA) in osteoarthritis: An in vitro and in vivo study, *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy* 125 (2020) 10984, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2020.109845>.

HOW TO CITE: Priyadarsini R., Hanitha Mathanke J.*, Archana S., Guhan G., Novel Quinazoline Derivatives as Experimental Inhibitors Of DDR-2 And ADAMTS-5: Design, Synthesis, Characterization, And QPCR Evaluation for The Treatment of Osteoarthritis, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (10), 563-586. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17392062>

